

Workshop - CS-Track - Analytics Workbench

welcome

Thank you for joining us!

We want to use this workshop to show you the Analytics Workbench which was created as part of the CS Track project.

Workshop - CS-Track - Analytics Workbench

WI01

To use the Analytics Workbench please open a separate tab and open workbench.rias-institute.eu/ please use the user "rias" and the password "cstrack" (both without the quotation marks)

The best way to see how the Workbench works is to analyse a project yourself which is why we prepared a list of projects for our workshop participants to use.

PHP code

```
urnDraw('project_names', 'IV01', 'now');  
html('Your project is: <b>'.value("IV01_01").'</b>');  
html('</br>The project name will be added on the coming pages whenever it is needed');
```

PHP code

```
html('</br>Your project is: <b>'.value("IV01_01").'</b></br></br>');
```

Analyzing a project

PA02

Navigate to "Analyse Project" and enter the project name, click on "Check Database", this prompts the workbench to check if there is any data on the project already saved. For the pre-selected projects the database already holds links and descriptions.

Once those loaded you should read the description to get an idea about the project. You may also correct any errors you find.

PA03

1. After reading the project description. Please name 2 (or more) research areas you can identify from the description.

01

PA04

2. Please name one Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) that relates to the project

You can find a list of the 17 existing SDGs here -> <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

 None

Click "Analyse Project" to continue with the analysis of the project.

PA05

Analysis results

AR01

3. What are the 2 most similar research areas?

AR02

For this please refer to the similarity score displayed next to the research area results

01

4. Do the assigned research areas match the textual description?

AR03

Please base your answer on the projects description and not on any additional knowledge you may have about the project.

- Yes
 No

5. What is the most similar SDG?

AR04

For this please refer to the similarity score displayed next to the SDG results

6. Do(es) the assigned SDG(s) match the projects description?

AR05

Please base your answer on the projects description and not on any additional knowledge you may have about the project.

- Yes
 No

7. Which organisation(s) is / are connected to the project? Please name one.

AR06

In the list of found named entities the left column shows the named entities and the right column assigns the corresponding label. Use this to find named entities classified as "ORG (Companies, agencies, institutions, etc.)"

The bigger context

ED01

Navigate to "Explore Data", the dashboard overview.

10. Which research area, SDG or named entity connects the project to most of the other projects?

You can use the first field to choose the displayed connectors and the second field to filter for your project in the network.

ED05

You can identify this using the bar chart in the explore data tab.

Name the research area

Name one project the research area is connected to (using the network view)

12. Which is the predominant SDG in the database?ED07

You can identify this using the bar chart in the explore data tab.

Name the SDG

Name one project the SDG is connected to (using the network view)

13. Choose one of the most common named entities, name it and one project it connects toED08

You can identify this using the bar chart in the explore data tab.

Name the named entity

Name one project the named entity is connected to (using the network view)

PHP code

```
html('</br>Your project is: <b>'.value("IV01_01").'</b></br></br>');
```

Generating recommendations

GR01

Navigate to "Find a project like ...". Here you can enter as many (or few) project names and research areas as you like to generate recommendations based on them.

14. Use the "Find a project like ..." tool to get recommendations based on the project you chose in the beginning, what do you enter and what are the first three results?

GR02

What did you enter?

Name the first three results

15. Find 3 project recommendations for someone interested in the project "Weather Rescue" and research related to "Meteorology & Atmospheric Sciences" and "Astronomy & Astrophysics"

GR03

Name the first three results

For the assessment of the Analytics Workbench as a whole, please fill out the following questionnaire. The question consists of pairs of contrasting attributes that may apply to the Workbench. The circles between the attributes represent gradations between the opposites. You can express your agreement with the attributes by ticking the circle that most closely reflects your impression.

UE01

16. Please decide spontaneously. Don't think too long about your decision to make sure that you convey your impression.

UE02

Sometimes you may not be completely sure about your agreement with a particular attribute or you may find that the attribute does not apply completely. Nevertheless, please tick a circle in every line.

It is your personal opinion that counts. Please remember: there is no wrong or right answer!

obstructive supportive

complicated easy

inefficient efficient

confusing clear

boring exiting

not interesting interesting

conventional inventive

usual leading edge

Feedback

EV01

Lastly we would greatly appreciate some feedback regarding the Analytics Workbench

17. Did the Analytics Workbench meet your expectations? Did anything surprise you?

EV02

18. What else would you have expected? Or which features would you wish were included?

EV03

19. Please rate the following features in terms of their helpfulness

EV04

	somewhat			
	not helpful	helpful	helpful	very helpful
assigned Research Areas per project	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
assigned SDGs per project	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
identified Named Entities per project	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
bar chart of Research Areas	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
bar chart of SDGs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
bar chart of Named Entities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Network View	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Recommendations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

20. Room to elaborate on the last question (e.g. What would have helped?)

EV05

21. In which role do you see yourself in in the Citizen Science context?

DD01

- Citizen Scientist / Volunteer
- Professional Scientist
- Research in Citizen Science
- Other

Thank you for completing this questionnaire!

We would like to thank you very much for helping us.

Your answers were transmitted, you may close the browser window or tab now.

[Cleo Schulten](#) at [RIAS](#) for the [CS Track](#) project – 2021